

EFFECT OF LOW FODMAP DIETARY PROGRAM ON SYMPTOMS CONTROL OF IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME AND QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG SAMPLE OF EGYPTIAN PATIENTS AT AIN SHAMS UNIVERSITY HOSPITALS.

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Abstract:

Background: A low-fermentable oligosaccharide, disaccharides, monosaccharides, and polyols (FODMAP) diet has been reported to be associated with improving the symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome (IBS); however, comparison between low FODMAP and the UK National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) dietary guideline for IBS still limited. **Objectives:** to determine the impact of low a FODMAP diet on symptom control and satisfaction of improvement in patients with IBS according to ROME IV criteria and IBS related quality of life and disability before and after participation; and to compare the impact of low FODMAP diet and NICE guidelines on symptoms control and quality of life among IBS patients. **Methods:** A randomized two-arm clinical trial had been conducted on 60 IBS patients who were randomized either to an intervention group (n=30) followed low FODMAP diet or a control group (n=30) followed NICE dietary guideline. **Results:** After 12 weeks of intervention, there was a statistically significant difference in (QOL) score and improvement of IBS symptoms ($p < 0.001$) between the intervention group and the control group, and there was a significant reduction ($p < 0.001$) in waist circumference among the intervention group versus the control group. In addition, patients in the intervention group were strongly satisfied ($p < 0.001$) than the control group **Conclusion:** a low FODMAP diet can improve global symptoms of IBS and quality of life more than NICE dietary guideline among group of Egyptian patients at Ain Shams University Hospitals.

Keywords: Egypt, Irritable bowel syndrome, Low FODMAP, Quality of Life, Symptoms Control

Introduction:

Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is a chronic functional disorder of gastrointestinal tract. It is characterized by abdominal pain or discomfort with abnormal bowel habit with the absence of biochemical or structural abnormalities [1].

IBS pathophysiology is complex and multifactorial, including altered gastrointestinal

motility, increased gastrointestinal fermentation, abnormal gas transit, visceral hypersensitivity, brain – gut axis dysregulation, dysbiosis of the gut microbiota, genetic predisposition and psychosocial aspects [2].

It is considered the most common gastrointestinal problem diagnosed in primary and secondary care and the most common reason for referral to gastroenterology clinics [1,3].

The pooled prevalence of IBS in 53 studies that used the Rome III criteria, from 38 countries and included 395 385 participants, was 9.2% (95% CI 7.6–10.8; $I^2=99.7\%$). By contrast, pooled IBS prevalence among six studies that used the Rome IV criteria was 3.8% from 34 countries and included 82 476 individuals (95% CI 3.1–4.5; $I^2=96.6\%$) [4].

Despite the fact that IBS is a non-life-threatening disorder with a lower life expectancy, it has a significant impact on patients' lives and the healthcare system. IBS is known to interfere with physical aspects of health-related quality of life (HRQOL), such as daily activities and work productivity. Patients with frequent bowel movements may find it difficult to go out and participate in daily activities such as work, travel, and other social/leisure activities. Avoiding all activities lowers QOL and may increase the risk of depression [5].

Treatment of IBS has historically been symptom-directed (e.g., bulking agents, antispasmodic agents) or centrally acting (e.g., antidepressants, cognitive–behavioral therapy), but the efficacy of these treatments is limited [6].

Dietary therapy for IBS has recently gained popularity, particularly diets low in fermentable oligosaccharides, disaccharides, monosaccharides, and polyols (FODMAPs). The lowering of FODMAPs in patient's diet may alleviate functional gastrointestinal symptoms by decreasing the transport of readily fermentable substrates and water to the distal small intestine and colon, which results in luminal distention and gas [7].

There are many examples of low FODMAP diets as: lactose free dairy products, hard cheese, fish, meat, chicken, shellfish, egg, pumpkin, potatoes, cucumber, leafy green, carrot, bananas, berries, kiwi, grapes, citrus fruit, gluten free bread, rice cereal, gluten free pasta, soy sauce, sugar, olives and olive oil. While High FODMAP diets such as: ice cream, soft cheese, yoghurt, cabbage, cauliflower, green beans, garlic, okra, onions, snow peas, broccoli, avocado, apple, mango, dates, watermelon, ripe banana, legumes, pulses, wheat, pasta and artificial sweeteners [8].

A number of uncontrolled clinical studies from Australia, New Zealand, Norway, the United Kingdom, Denmark, and Spain have repeatedly demonstrated the usefulness of a low FODMAP diet in the treatment of IBS. Five controlled trials provide solid evidence for the efficacy of low FODMAP diet. At a 2 to 6 months follow-up visits, significantly more patients on low FODMAP diet reported improvement in overall symptoms as well as satisfaction with response compared to those who received NICE dietary advice [6].

According to our knowledge, there are no studies in Egypt that reveal the effect of a low FODMAP diet on IBS symptoms and quality of life for IBS patients. Therefore, the current study was conducted to determine the impact of low FODMAP diet on symptoms control and satisfaction of improvement in patients with IBS according to ROME IV criteria, evaluate the impact of the

intervention program in a term of IBS related quality of life (QOL) and disability before and after participation, and to compare the impact of low FODMAP diet and standard dietary advice of the UK National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE).

Subjects and Methods:

An interventional randomized two arm clinical trial had been used on two groups of IBS patients. The intervention group followed a low FODMAP diet and a control group followed the NICE dietary guideline, subjects were recruited from Family Medicine and Internal Medicine Outpatient clinics at Ain Shams University Hospitals in Cairo, Egypt. All adults aged from 18-50 years' who were diagnosed with IBS according to ROME IV criteria were eligible for inclusion in this study through a purposive sample. **Exclusion Criteria:** Age of 50 years old or older, unintentional weight loss, change in the symptom quality (e.g., new and different pain), night time symptoms as that awake the individual, blood in stool, pregnant females and chronic debilitating disease. Random allocation (sequentially numbered opaque sealed envelopes) was used to assign patients with IBS either to the intervention group or to the control group.

Sample Size was calculated according to results of a study comparing symptom response following advice for a low in fermentable carbohydrates versus standard dietary advice in patients with IBS conducted in 2011. Level of confidence 95%, power 90%, proportion of improvement of symptoms of IBS of low FODMAP diet: 86%, proportion of improvement of symptoms of IBS on ordinary diet advice: 49%. The sample size in every group:24, proportion of expected lost follow-up:15%. Final sample size raised to 30 participants in each group. Sample size was calculated using EPIDAT software version 4.1.

Study phases and data collection tools:

Assessment phase (for both groups): this phase was conducted through an Arabic interview questionnaire and full clinical examination including general and local abdominal examination which was carried out to detect any abnormality, and to measure waist circumference. The interview questionnaire consists of two parts: Socio demographic data (age, gender, education, occupation, income, residence, marital status, etc [9]), and symptoms of IBS according to ROME IV criteria [10], this interview took approximately about 20-25 minutes.

Implementation phase:

During the first visit (for both intervention and control groups): A cognitive part had been implemented in the waiting area (a power point simplified lecture): it was done once in the first visit in about 30 minutes with the objective of improving the patient's knowledge and attitude towards IBS, etiology, symptoms and complications, treatment and importance of taking prescribed medications regularly, regular scheduled follow up appointments, and to understand the importance of following dietary instructions and the researcher answered questions in Arabic.

For the intervention group: During the first visit: The researcher explained the benefits of a **low FODMAP** diet in controlling IBS symptoms. A brochure of the allowed and forbidden food (low

FODMAP diet) was given [8] with giving an example of a dietary program including details of preferred food in breakfast, lunch, dinner and snacks patients followed it for about 12 weeks. A dietary sheet was given to each patient to record three main meals and snacks consumed throughout the day for the follow-up period.

All subjects in the intervention group were followed up for twelve weeks according to the study carried out by **Staudacher et al [14]** who found that a low FODMAP diet was more effective than the ordinary dietary advice for symptom control of IBS in eight weeks duration and we added another four weeks of follow up, every week through phone call, and a medical appointment every two weeks to ensure adherence of patients and to show the effect of a low FODMAP dietary intervention on symptoms of IBS.

For the Control group: They were educated on instructions of NICE dietary guidelines for IBS as: healthy eating principles (e.g. regular eating, taking time to eat). Limiting high fat foods, ensure a good intake of non-caffeinated fluids, limiting fizzy drinks as well as limiting insoluble fiber for diarrhea and increase gradually for constipation; limiting sugar free sweets and foods containing sorbitol; limiting fruit to 3 portions a day; avoiding resistant starch may be useful (e.g. pulses, sweetcorn, green bananas, part-baked and reheated bread) and addition of oats and linseeds may be helpful [11]. a dietary sheet was given for the first 2 weeks of intervention. No regular follow up visits for control group, only one medical appointment after two weeks had been done to include a full clinical examination, local abdominal examination and IBS global improvement scale.

Evaluation phase (for both groups): Full clinical examination (general and local abdominal examination) and final waist circumference was measured, symptoms changes were rated for each patient as bloating, abdominal pain/discomfort, flatulence/wind, diarrhea, constipation, nausea and energy levels using a seven-point Likert scale taken from the **validated IBS Global Improvement Scale** (substantially worse, moderately worse, slightly worse, no change, slightly improved, moderately improved, substantially improved, or never had the symptom) every two weeks [12]. The intervention group completed this scale at every visit, while the control group completed it only at the initial and final visits.

For both intervention and control groups immediately after implementation of the intervention program, each patient fulfilled **Global IBS quality of life scale:** it was conducted at the first and the last visit through the finalized IBS-36 which consisted of 36 questions and was then translated into Arabic. The IBS-36 asks patients to think about the impact of their IBS symptoms on their QOL and is then scored on a 7-point Likert scale where 0 never and 6 always. A final score is a sum of the scores of the 36 questions, with question 18 being reverse scored (i.e., for a patient score of 0, a score of 6 is entered). The highest possible score on the IBS-36 is 216, and the lowest is 0, higher scores indicating worse symptoms and poorer IBS specific QOL [13].

Patient satisfaction scale: The scale included satisfaction with symptom improvement, easiness of following dietary intervention, understanding of written information and changing diet to

improve symptoms'. These statements were scored using a five-point Likert scale (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree) [14].

Data management and statistical Analysis: Data were tabulated and statistically analyzed using SPSS, version 20. Description of data were expressed as mean and standard deviation (minimum – maximum) for quantitative data, and frequencies (n) and percentage (%) for qualitative data. p value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Consideration: The study was carried out at Ain Shams University Hospital after obtaining board approval from administration and the ethics committee (*Approval no. FWA000017585*). Informed consent was obtained from all patients. Confidentiality of data was assured.

Results:

The current study found no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the intervention and control groups as regards age of participants, and socioeconomic status scale, indicating effective randomization (Table 1).

At baseline, there was no significant difference in Waist circumference between the intervention and control groups; but after 12 weeks, there was significant reduction in Waist circumference among the intervention group versus the control group (Table 2).

In terms of QOL score before intervention, there was no significant difference between the intervention and control groups, but it is noticeable that after 12 weeks of intervention, there was a considerable drop in IBS symptom severity and improvement of QOL among the intervention group (Table 3).

In addition, there was a statistically significant difference between the intervention and control group in reporting ease of understanding of the written information, acceptance of further change to their diet to improve their symptoms, and satisfaction with symptom improvement (Table 4).

During the entire follow-up period, there was a statistically significant difference on the IBS Global Improvement Scale among intervention group (Table 5).

At the end of the intervention, the intervention group showed a significant improvement of IBS symptoms, as well as there was a statistically significant difference between the intervention and control groups in the patient Satisfaction Scale (Table 6).

Intervention by a low FODMAP diet was significant predictor for decrease in IBS severity of symptoms and improvement of QOL by 59.175, and socioeconomic score was also significant predictor for improvement of QOL by 1.180 (Table 7).

Discussion:

Supported by other researches, this study found that the Low FODMAP diet is effective in controlling symptoms of IBS, especially at the level of pain, abdominal distension, diarrhea and improving quality of life as reducing FODMAP sugar consumption reduces fermentation within the colon, therefore, the osmotic impact reduces the amount of liquid entering the intestinal lumen, whereas colonic bacterial fermentation produces gas and volatile fatty acids.

Regarding waist circumference comparison between intervention group and control group after 12 weeks of intervention, the current study showed that there was significant reduction in the intervention group versus the control group, these study findings were in concordance with study carried out by **Guerreiro et al [15]** who found individuals of the Low FODMAP group showed a significant decrease in weight, body mass index, abdominal circumference, and percentage of fat mass after four weeks of exclusion of FODMAPs. However, another study by **Bellini et al [16]** reported that anthropometric data did not change significantly after an 8-week Low FODMAP diet; this difference could be related to the study's small sample size.

Regarding comparison between the effect of low FODMAP diet and NICE dietary advice on symptoms improvement of IBS, the current study showed that low FODMAP diet had significant improvement of IBS symptoms over NICE dietary advice, and this finding agreed with a study carried out by **Eswaran et al [17]** on eighty-four subjects which found the low FODMAP diet led to greater reductions in average daily scores of abdominal pain, bloating, consistency, frequency, and urgency than the modified NICE dietary advice. These findings are also supported by another study conducted by **Patcharatrakul et al [18]** on 62 patients, which revealed that global IBS symptom severity improved considerably.

This study's findings are in line with those of **Staudacher et al [14]** who observed that patients in the low FODMAP group were more satisfied with their symptom response (76%) than those in the standard group (54%) ($P = 0.038$). the low FODMAP group (86%) had a better overall symptom response than the standard group (49%) ($P = 0.001$). Bloating (low FODMAP 82% vs. standard 49%, $P = 0.002$), stomach pain (low FODMAP 85% vs. standard 61%, $P = 0.023$), and flatulence (low FODMAP 87% vs. standard 50%, $P = 0.001$) were all considerably reduced in the low FODMAP group.

On the other hand, the current study finding disagreed with a study carried out by **Böhn et al [19]** on 67 patients who completed the dietary intervention. The severity of IBS symptoms was reduced in both groups during the intervention, without a significant difference between the groups ($P = .62$), This could be explained by the fact that the group given typical dietary recommendations likewise avoided foods high in FODMAPs.

Regarding Comparison of Quality of life between the intervention and control groups, and before and after intervention; when comparing the intervention and control groups, there was considerable improvement of quality of life in the intervention group, and this result was consistent with a meta-analysis study conducted by **Lanen et al [20]** and another meta-analysis study on twenty-two publications conducted by **Hahn et al [21]** indicated that the low FODMAP group

showed a moderate reduction in symptom severity and a slight increase in QOL when compared to the control group .

Also, this study finding in concordance with study carried out by **Kortlever et al [22]** on 111 patients which found that there were significant improvements in QoL from baseline (both $P < 0.001$).

On the other hand, the current study findings were in contrast to a meta-analysis conducted by **Wang et al [23]** on five studies, which found no significant changes in QOL ($n = 484$; MD = 2.77; 95 percent CI 2 to 7.55; I² = 62 percent). This difference could be due to the fact that most LFD trials were short (8 weeks), and an additional period may be required for clinically significant improvement in quality of life for IBS patients.

Regarding Comparison of patient satisfaction score between the intervention and control groups; the study findings were the same as the findings of the study carried out by **Roest et al [24]** on 192 patients with IBS as he found (72.1%) patients were satisfied with their overall symptoms. In total, (89.5%) of those studied thought that the written information was easy to understand, while (60%) of patients stated that the diet was easy to follow, (65.1%) could easily find suitable products and (43.5%) were able to incorporate the diet easily into their life. And about (18.2%) believed that simply being given a list of foods to avoid, it would have been as effective as seeing the dietitian for a consultation.

Furthermore, the current study findings were similar to a study carried out by **Staudacher et al [14]** which found that in total, (76%) patients in the low FODMAP group reported satisfaction with their symptom response compared to (54%) in the standard group ($P = 0.038$). There were no differences between the groups when reporting ease of understanding the written information (low FODMAP 100% versus standard 94%, $P = 0.116$) or ease of following the diet (low FODMAP 70% versus standard 85%, $P = 0.112$). More patients in the low FODMAP group were interested in implementing further change to their diet to improve their symptoms (low FODMAP 25% versus standard 5%, $P = 0.014$).

Alternatively, another study carried out by **Reg et al [25]** who aimed to compare the efficacy and acceptability of the low FODMAP diet (**LFD**) and gluten free diet (**GFD**) against traditional dietary advice (TDA) to improve IBS symptoms on 33 individuals per arm (total=99) which found that the diets did not significantly differ in clinical efficacy, with 42%–58% experiencing a ≥ 50 -point reduction in IBS symptom severity score (IBS-SSS). Responders had similar improvements in IBS-SSS items regardless of their allocated diet, but individuals found TDA cheaper, less time-consuming to shop, and easier to follow when eating out than the GFD and LFD. It was also easier to implement into everyday life than the LFD, this finding may be due to overlap between 3 dietary interventions in many foods.

Conclusion: A diet low in fermentable oligosaccharides, disaccharides, monosaccharides, and polyols (FODMAP) is an effective intervention to control irritable bowel syndrome symptoms and improve quality of life compared to NICE dietary guidelines for IBS, also noted a low

FODMAP diet can cause significant reduction in waist circumference among the intervention group in comparison to the control group.

Recommendation:

Family physicians should increase awareness of how to follow a low FODMAP diet and its importance in controlling symptoms for their patients with IBS as it will improve their QOL. They should also make patients aware that after following a low FODMAP diet, they can reintroduce a high FODMAP meal one at a time, every 3 days, to observe if it triggers any unwanted symptoms. If a high FODMAP meal causes symptoms, it is advised to avoid it long term (this is referred to as a personalized diet).

References:

1. National Medicines Information Centre. IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME. NMIC Bulletin. 2015;21(4).
2. Raskov, H., Burcharth, J., Pommergaard, H. C., & Rosenberg, J. Irritable bowel syndrome, the microbiota and the gut-brain axis. *Gut microbes*, 7(5), 365–383, 2016 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19490976.2016.1218585>
3. Ford, Alexander & Moayyedi, Paul & Chey, William & Harris, Lucinda & Lacy, Brian & Saito, Yuri & Quigley, Eamonn. American College of Gastroenterology Monograph on Management of Irritable Bowel Syndrome. *The American Journal of Gastroenterology* (2018). 113. 1. 10.1038/s41395-018-0084-x.
4. Oka, Priya & Parr, Heather & Barberio, Brigida & Black, Christopher & Savarino, Edoardo & Ford, Alexander. Global prevalence of irritable bowel syndrome according to Rome III or IV criteria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Gastroenterology & Hepatology*. 5. 10.1016/S2468-1253(20)30217-X ,2020.
5. Kopczyńska, M., Mokros, Ł., Pietras, T., & Małecka-Panas, E. Quality of life and depression in patients with irritable bowel syndrome. *Przegląd gastroenterologiczny*, 13(2), 102–108. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5114/pg.2018.75819>
6. Molina-Infante J, Serra J, Fernandez-Bañares F, Mearin F. The low-FODMAP diet for irritable bowel syndrome: Lights and shadows. *Gastroenterol Hepatol*. Feb;39(2):55-65, 2016. doi: 10.1016/j.gastrohep.2015.07.009. Epub 2015 Nov 6. PMID: 26548734.
7. Magge S, Lembo A. Low-FODMAP Diet for Treatment of Irritable Bowel Syndrome. *Gastroenterol Hepatol (N Y)*.;8(11):739-745,2012.
8. Halland M, Saito YA. Irritable bowel syndrome: new and emerging treatments. *BMJ*. Jun 18;350:h1622, 2015 doi: 10.1136/bmj.h1622. PMID: 26088265
9. El-Gilany, Abdel-Hady & El-Wehady, A & Elwasify, Mahmoud.. Updating and validation of the socioeconomic status scale for health research in Egypt. *Eastern Mediterranean health journal = La revue de santé de la Méditerranée orientale = al-Majallah al-ṣiḥḥīyah li-sharq al-mutawassiṭ*. 18. 962-8. 10.26719/2012.18.9.962. 2012.
10. Drossman DA Functional gastrointestinal disorders: history, pathophysiology, clinical features, and Rome IV. *Gastroenterology*. 150: 1262–7900. 2016. DOI: 10.1053/j.gastro.2016.02.032.

11. National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) . Irritable bowel syndrome in adults. Diagnosis and management of irritable bowel syndrome in primary care ,2008. Available at <http://www.nice.org.uk/nicemedia/live/11927/39622/39622.pdf>. (Accessed on 20 May 2010).
12. Gordon S, Ameen V, Bagby B, Shahan B, Jhingran P, Carter E. Validation of irritable bowel syndrome Global Improvement Scale: an integrated symptom end point for assessing treatment efficacy. *Dig Dis Sci*. Jul;48(7):1317-23,2003. doi: 10.1023/a:1024159226274. PMID: 12870789.
13. Dianne Groll, M.Sc., Stephen J. Vanner, M.D., William T. Depew, M.D., F.A.C.G., Laurington R. DaCosta, M.D and William G. Paterson .The IBS-36: A New Quality of Life Measure for Irritable Bowel Syndrome. *The American Journal of Gastroenterology*. Vol. 97, No. 4, 2002. by Am. Coll. of Gastroenterology ISSN 0002-9270/02/\$22.00. Published by Elsevier Science Inc. PII S0002-9270(02)03972-2.
14. Staudacher H.M . Whelan K . Irving P. M . Lomer M. C. E Comparison of symptom response following advice for a diet low in fermentable carbohydrates (FODMAPs) versus standard dietary advice in patients with irritable bowel syndrome. *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics* © 2011 The British Dietetic Association Ltd. Vol 24, No 5 :487-495 , 2011. First published: 25 May 2011 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-277X.2011.01162>
15. Guerreiro MM, Santos Z, Carolino E, et al. Effectiveness of Two Dietary Approaches on the Quality of Life and Gastrointestinal Symptoms of Individuals with Irritable Bowel Syndrome. *J Clin Med*;9(1):125, 2020. Published 2020 Jan 2. doi:10.3390/jcm9010125.
16. Bellini, Massimo & Tonarelli, Sara & Barracca, Federico & Morganti, Riccardo & Pancetti, Andrea & Bertani, Lorenzo & De Bortoli, Nicola & Costa, Francesco & Mosca, Marta & Marchi, Santino & Rossi, Alessandra. A Low-FODMAP Diet for Irritable Bowel Syndrome: Some Answers to the Doubts from a Long-Term Follow-Up. *Nutrients*. 12. 2360. 10.3390/nu12082360, 2020.
17. Eswaran SL, Chey WD, Han-Markey T, Ball S, Jackson K. A Randomized Controlled Trial Comparing the Low FODMAP Diet vs. Modified NICE Guidelines in US Adults with IBS-D. *Am J Gastroenterol*Dec;111(12):1824-1832, 2016. doi: 10.1038/ajg.2016. 434. Epub 2016 Oct 11. PMID: 27725652.
18. Patcharatrakul T, Juntrapirat A, Lakananurak N, Gonlachanvit S. Effect of Structural Individual Low-FODMAP Dietary Advice vs. Brief Advice on a Commonly Recommended Diet on IBS Symptoms and Intestinal Gas Production. *Nutrients*. Nov 21;11(12):2856,2019. doi: 10.3390/nu11122856. PMID: 31766497; PMCID: PMC6950148.
19. Böhn L, Störsrud S, Liljebo T, et al. Diet low in FODMAPs reduces symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome as well as traditional dietary advice: a randomized controlled trial. *Gastroenterology*;149(6):1399-1407.e1392, 2015
20. Van Lanen AS, de Bree A, Greyling A. Efficacy of a low-FODMAP diet in adult irritable bowel syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur J Nutr*. Sep;60(6):3505-3522, 2021 doi:

10.1007/s00394-020-02473-0. Epub 2021 Feb 14. Erratum in: Eur J Nutr. 2021 Jun 28; PMID: 33585949; PMCID: PMC8354978.

21. Hahn J, Choi J, Chang MJ. Effect of Low FODMAPs Diet on Irritable Bowel Syndromes: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Clinical Trials. *Nutrients.*; 13(7):2460, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13072460>.
22. Kortlever TL, Ten Bokkel Huinink S, Offereins M, Hebblethwaite C, O'Brien L, Leeper J, Mulder CJJ, Barrett JS, Garry RB. Low-FODMAP Diet Is Associated with Improved Quality of Life in IBS Patients-A Prospective Observational Study. *Nutr Clin Pract.* Aug;34(4):623-630,2019. doi: 10.1002/ncp.10233. Epub 2019 Jan 15. PMID: 30644587.
23. Wang J, Yang P, Zhang L, Hou X. A Low-FODMAP Diet Improves the Global Symptoms and Bowel Habits of Adult IBS Patients: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Front Nutr.* Aug 19; 8:683191, 2021. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2021.683191. PMID: 34490319; PMCID: PMC8417072.
24. de Roest RH, Dobbs BR, Chapman BA, Batman B, O'Brien LA, Leeper JA, Hebblethwaite CR, Garry RB. The low FODMAP diet improves gastrointestinal symptoms in patients with irritable bowel syndrome: a prospective study. *Int J Clin Pract.* Sep;67(9):895-903, 2013. doi: 10.1111/ijcp.12128. Epub 2013 May 23. PMID: 23701141.
25. Rej A, Sanders DS, Shaw CC, Buckle R, Trott N, Agrawal A, Aziz I. Efficacy and Acceptability of Dietary Therapies in Non-Constipated Irritable Bowel Syndrome: A Randomized Trial of Traditional Dietary Advice, the Low FODMAP Diet, and the Gluten-Free Diet. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol.* Feb 28:S1542-3565(22)00202-6, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.cgh.2022.02.045. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 35240330.

Table 1. Patients' sociodemographic among intervention and control groups

		Intervention N=30	Control N=30	P
		N (%) / Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	N (%) / Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	
Age		34.1 ± 8.9 (18-50)	34.6 ± 9.2 (18-50)	.809
Gender #	Male	8 (26.7)	8 (26.7)	1.000
	Female	22 (73.3)	22 (73.3)	
Marital status ‡	Single	5 (16.7)	6 (20)	1.000
	Married	24 (80)	23 (76.7)	
	Divorced	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	
	Widow	0 (0)	0 (0)	
Education ‡	Illiterate	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	.817
	Read & write	0 (0)	0 (0)	
	Primary	0 (0)	0 (0)	
	Preparatory	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	
	Secondary	3 (10)	4 (13.3)	
	Higher institute	2 (6.7)	5 (16.7)	
	University	23 (76.7)	19 (63.3)	
	PG	0 (0)	0 (0)	
Occupation ‡	Not working	7 (23.3)	9 (30)	.988
	manual worker	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	
	skilled manual worker	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	
	Freelance	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	
	Semi-professional/clerk	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	
	Professional	18 (60)	16 (53.3)	
Socioeconomic status scale		41.4±6 (22-51)	39.2±5.4 (22-47)	.146

(#) chi square test and (‡) Fisher exact test were used.

Table 2. Before and after 12 weeks waist circumference comparison between intervention and control groups

	Intervention	Control	P #
	Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	
Waist circumference Before intervention	95.2 ± 12.5 (70-120)	97.8 ± 11.4 (80-120)	.409
Waist circumference	88.6 ± 11.5 (65-109)	95.6 ± 10.5 (79-118)	.*018

After intervention		
P †	.000*	.000*

(#) Independent t test and (†) Paired t test were used.

Table 3. Comparison of quality of life between the intervention and control groups, before and after intervention:

	Intervention	Control	P #
	Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	
QOL score before intervention	129±26.1 (83-166)	126±26.5 (73-172)	.661
QOL score after intervention	52.8±6.2 (44-70)	114.5±22.6 (69-148)	.000*
P †	.000*	.000*	

(#) Independent t test and (†) Paired t test were used.

Table 4. Patient satisfaction scale among the intervention group and control group:

		Intervention	Control	P
		N (%)	N (%)	
I found the written information easy to understand	4	4(13.3)	15(50)	.002*
	5	26(86.7)	15(50)	
I found the diet easy to follow i.e. I could Find suitable food products and incorporate it into my life easily.	2	2(6.7)	3(10)	.105
	3	6(20)	7(23.3)	
	4	11(36.7)	17(56.7)	
	5	11(36.7)	3(10)	
Overall, I am satisfied with the improvement in my symptoms	1	0(0)	4(13.3)	.000*
	2	0(0)	16(53.3)	
	3	0(0)	9(30)	
	4	2(6.7)	1(3.3)	
	5	28(93.3)	0(0)	
I would be interested in further changing in my Diet to improve my symptoms	3	0(0)	2(6.7)	.000*
	4	7(23.3)	20(66.7)	
	5	23(76.7)	8(26.7)	

(#) chi square test and (‡) Fisher exact test were used.

1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree

Table 5. The change in IBS Global Improvement Scale over the follow up period among the intervention group:

Improvement Scale over follow up period	Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	P
IBS Global Improvement Scale 1	28.3±2.6 (22-34)	.000*
IBS Global Improvement Scale 2	31.4±2.9 (27-37)	
IBS Global Improvement Scale 3	35.7±3.2 (29-40)	
IBS Global Improvement Scale 4	40.7±3.9 (30-47)	
IBS Global Improvement Scale 5	44.7±4.3 (35-49)	
IBS Global Improvement Scale 6	45.3±4.2 (35-49)	

Repeated measure ANOVA was used to assess the overall difference over the whole follow up period. And paired t test was used to assess between individual follow up points with each other (P value for all = < .001)

Table 6. Comparison of final IBS Global Improvement Scale and Patient satisfaction score between the intervention and control groups:

	Intervention	Control	P #
	Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	Mean ± SD (Min – Max)	
Final IBS Global Improvement Scale	45.30 ± 4.22 (35 – 49)	27.87 ± 3.14 (19 – 33)	.000*
Patient satisfaction score	18.6±1.1 (16-20)	14.6±1.6 (12-19)	.000*

(#) Independent t test was used.

Table 7. Linear regression for identifying the predictors of QOL score after intervention period

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	p	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	170.433	17.230		.000	135.889	204.976
Age	-.259	.271	-.066	.344	-.802	.285
Gender	3.266	5.956	.041	.586	-8.676	15.208
Marital status	-3.462	6.998	-.044	.623	-17.493	10.569
Socioeconomic score	-1.180	.366	-.193	.002*	-1.914	-.445
Intervention	-59.175	4.038	-.849	.000*	-67.270	-51.080

(R squared =.826; P value of ANOVA test =.000)
*statistically significant